

SPACES OF SPACES — INTERACTIVE NAVIGATION IN CORPORA OF ROOM IMPULSE RESPONSES FOR MUSICAL PRODUCTION AND CREATION

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ABSTRACT

We will present the first results of the RIRIRI project (Room Impulse Response Interactive Retrieval and Inspection) treating collections of room impulse responses (RIRs) and their perceptual description, visual representation, and interactive retrieval of IRs by using spatio-timbral content descriptors. We employ established audio analysis techniques and 2D interaction paradigms from the CataRT system for corpus-based concatenative synthesis, providing an efficient, intuitive, and user-friendly means of navigating RIR collections based on perceptual and spatial attributes. The developed proof of concept application can render (auralise) RIRs either using convolution, or via approximation by a parametric reverb. There is a growing number of RIR collections available for which interactive navigation in a 2D descriptor space provides a more intuitive access than scrolling through lists, unlocking the true richness of these collections, and allowing creative applications of playing with and composing acoustic spaces.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, sound artists and designers can leverage an ever growing number of room impulse response (RIR) collections. These are constituted of impulse responses (IRs) captured in various acoustic spaces, and usable in convolution reverbs.¹ Each collection can contain IRs of hundreds of different spaces, making the task of choosing an appropriate IR by scrolling through a list of names (which are not necessarily informative about the precise sound character of the space), and sometimes complemented by numerical or textual metadata, quite tedious and unappealing.

To alleviate this, and to add a more creative and intuitive use to RIR collections, we propose to apply interactive navigation in a 2D audio descriptor vector space, as used for corpus-based concatenative synthesis (CBCS). In the context of sound sample libraries, CBCS has proven a

¹ Examples are: *EchoThief* library, Ableton Live *Hybrid* reverb, York Uni *Open AIR* library, and many others. These RIRs are usually captured in typical rooms, concert halls, churches, etc. but often also contain outdoor settings or totally unconventional spaces. Collections may also contain IRs emulating analog reverberator units (spring, plate) or “classic” algorithmic reverb devices.

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creative tool to unlock the true richness of sound collections [1]. The audio descriptors used for our proof of concept implementation are standard timbre descriptors, with the addition of a few room acoustic criteria as metadata (reverb time and early reflection). In this paper we will provide strong hints that even just the timbre descriptors alone provide a highly intuitive and creative approach to finding a specific RIR, and the interactive browsing invites to *play and compose with acoustic spaces* by navigating the timbre space. Some timbre descriptors also gain surprising new perceptual interpretations when applied to RIRs, as we will see later. In order to listen to a RIR selected by interactive retrieval using the 2D spatial interaction paradigm, a user-chosen test or example signal is convolved with the currently selected IR(s).

In this article, we will focus on exploring the following three use cases of the proposed proof of concept application, illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the three proposed use cases.

Browse: Exploring the RIR corpus according to the audio descriptor dimensions with the aim of choosing one existing RIR that the user likes.

Hybridise: Interactive creative navigation and hybridisation (mixing) of RIRs with the dynamic interpolation/transition between several existing IRs, there-

fore producing a new time-varying space or a new hybrid IR that was not in the original collections. The newly interpolated IR can be either auralised or exported to a new IR file.

Mimic: Examining collections of IRs produced by (black box) reverb plugins, the relation of their (specific and opaque) parameters to perceptual attributes, and their approximation by algorithmic reverberators using shared and unified parameters.

2. PREVIOUS WORK

2.1 Room Acoustics and Control of Artificial Reverberators

Artificial reverberation is an essential element of music or film production. It is used by audio engineers and sound designers for adding a sensation of space and depth to audio recordings or electronic tracks. Depending on the artist's intent, reverberation processors can be used to emulate/mimic the acoustic characteristics of real-world spaces, or simply as a special effect, possibly evoking unnatural spaces.

2.1.1 Techniques for Artificial Reverberation

Over the past 60 years, various techniques have been developed to generate artificial reverberation [2]. Amongst the different artificial reverberation approaches, convolution and delay-based reverberators are usually preferred in the context of music production. Convolution reverbs exploit impulse responses (IRs) typically captured by acoustic measurements in existing spaces. These IRs characterise the transfer path, i.e., the reverberation fingerprint between an emitter and a receiver in space. Offering a “realistic” auralisation experience, convolution-based processors have become very popular in the last decades thanks to the development of computationally efficient, low latency FFT-based algorithms [3]. For creative transformations of the reverb effect, convolution-based engines are usually limited to a few low-level parameters, such as adjusting the early/late ratio or varying the decay time.

Algorithmic delay-based reverberators, on the other hand, are based on networks of delay lines and digital filters. A wide variety of architectures, typically involving comb and/or allpass filters, have been proposed [2]. Currently, Feedback Delay Networks (FDN) [4] are the most commonly used topology as they provide flexible control of the temporal and spectral decay attributes. Parametric reverbs offer the flexibility to design a wide range of effects, from natural-sounding to surreal spaces.

2.1.2 Tuning of Reverbs

The tuning of the reverb engines, either convolution-based or parametric, depends entirely on the manufacturer's implementation or used algorithm. Parameters exposed to the end-user generally include [5]: reverberation time at -60 dB (RT_{60}) in two or three frequency bands, pre-delay, and density/diffusion of early reflections. A delay-based reverberator may be used to synthesise the main decay characteristics of an RIR (RT_{60}). However, this type

of reverberator requires some considerations to ensure that their internal parameters (delay-line lengths, recirculation matrix) will result in accurate synthesis [6].

2.1.3 IR Descriptors / Metrics

The choice of these control parameters is sometimes—but not always—influenced by knowledge from the field of room acoustics. Indeed, extensive scientific research has focused on the architectural design of auditoria (concert halls, opera houses, theatres, etc.) and on the objective characterisation and perceptual evaluation of their room acoustical quality [7, 8]. In particular, research on the objective characterisation of the acoustics of performance spaces has led to the definition and standardisation (ISO-3382) of a set of objective criteria, including: reverberation decay time (RT_{60}), early decay time (Edt), early-to-late energy ratio (C50, C80), strength (G), lateral energy fraction (LF), or interaural cross-correlation coefficient (IACC) [9, 10]. These metrics can be estimated from measured IRs, and they are widely adopted by acousticians. They are generally recognised as relevant descriptors of our listening experience in music venues.

2.1.4 Link between Objective Descriptors and Perceptual Attributes

However, the relationship between these objective descriptors and the perceptual listening experience is complex and not yet fully elucidated. Several investigations have sought to exhibit a minimal set of subjective parameters suitable for explaining or predicting listener sensations or preference judgments, or revealing correlations between measurable parameters and sensory attributes [11–17]. Such perceptual factors include notably: loudness, reverberance, running reverberance, clarity, intimacy, warmth, and spaciousness [9].

2.1.5 Perceptual Model for Controlling Reverberators

Using such correlations between acoustical descriptors and perceptual factors, the Ircam Room Acoustics team proposed in the 1980s-1990s a perceptual model for controlling reverberators (see e.g. [18, 19] for details). The model consists of a concise set of mutually independent subjective attributes, i.e. it forms a low-dimensionality (11) perceptual space in which any reverb setting can be represented. This mutual independence (orthogonality) is important for the uniqueness of the description and, in practice, to ensure that modifying the setting of a given perceptual attribute will affect as little as possible the sensations controlled by adjusting other perceptual attributes in the set. The model is implemented in Ircam Spat's reverb engine [20].

2.1.6 Limitations of the Spat Perceptual Model

Although the Spat perceptual model has proven useful in a number of artistic productions, it is also limited and cannot be directly applied to the categorisation of arbitrary collections of IRs. Indeed, the model was established based on the analysis of medium-sized “conventional” auditoria and concert halls [18, 19]. There is evidence that the model

is not sufficient to grasp the details of more complex architectural volumes [17], where for example the assumption of an isotropic late diffuse field may not hold [21]. Furthermore, the model is likely not to be suitable for other “atypical” reverberant spaces such as large outdoor squares, forests, corridors, etc.

2.2 Perceptual Timbre Spaces and Corpus-based Synthesis

The concept of timbre space was introduced by Grey, Wessel, and McAdams [22–24] in psychoacoustics research as a model of human perception of timbre, or *sound colour*, where relative distances between sounds in a low-dimensional space correspond to relative dissimilarity of timbre perception. Wessel already envisioned this representation as the basis for musical composition by “taking a walk in timbre space” [23]. This concept was realised in the work on corpus-based concatenative synthesis [25, 26], using navigation through a (usually 2D-projected) vector space of audio descriptors as the main interface for playing and composing music [27].

2.2.1 Audio Descriptors

These audio descriptors are calculated by signal processing methods to estimate features of the audio signal that have a close relation to human auditory perception [28]. Some of these methods rely on time-domain audio analysis, but most are based on a spectral representation of the signal, possibly after applying a perceptual weighting model to account for the frequency-specific sensitivity of the human ear [29]. These descriptors are usually instantaneous, i.e. they describe the timbre of a short signal frame. In order to describe a whole segment of sound, temporal modeling has to be applied, consisting usually of taking basic statistics like the mean or maximum of the instantaneous descriptor values of the segment.

2.2.2 Creative Convolution for Articulating Corpus-based Synthesis

The link between convolution and timbre spaces had previously been made by Schwarz, Tremblay and Harker [30] where grains from a corpus of musical or voice sounds were used as IRs to be convolved with a contact microphone signal in order to articulate the corpus sounds by intuitive contact interaction on any surface or object. This can also be seen the other way around in that the contact interaction sound gets imprinted with the timbre of the corpus sounds. They also introduced distance-based mixing of several convolution voices to create a smooth sonic interaction space.

3. RIR DESCRIPTORS

For this proof of concept of interactive room impulse response browsing, we used 8 existing timbre descriptors for general audio signals, and 4 specialised room acoustics descriptors, listed in table 1.

3.1 Timbre Descriptors

The existing general timbre descriptors are those of the CATART system [31] based on the MUBU² [32] extension package for the MAX audio programming environment.

When sound files are imported into the audio corpus, the analysis module calculates 8 audio descriptors: fundamental frequency (pitch), periodicity (corresponding to the continuum between tonal and noisy sounds), and first order autocorrelation coefficient (expressing spectral tilt), estimated by the time-based *yin* algorithm [33]; loudness, and spectral descriptors centroid (the center of gravity of the spectrum [29], corresponding to the perceived brightness of a sound), spread, skewness, kurtosis (describing the overall shape and distribution of the spectrum).

The time-varying instantaneous descriptors calculated at a period of 6 ms have to be condensed to summarise each of the varying-length RIR signals by a fixed number of values. For this *temporal modeling* stage we simply calculate the mean value of each descriptor over each segment, but the standard deviation, min, max, or slope could also be used to more precisely summarise the evolution of each descriptor over the duration of an IR.

3.2 Room Acoustics Descriptors

Additionally to the audio timbre descriptors, we load pre-computed estimations of reverb time at -60 dB (RT_{60}), in 7 frequency bands f (RT_{60f} , see table 1), and the 20 first early reflection onset times and amplitudes (ERT, ER-A). These are calculated off-line by Matlab scripts and saved to a text file. The precomputed values are then merged with the timbre descriptors calculated in the Max patch. The RT_{60} is calculated using the energy decay slope of the RIR [34]. More specifically, the reverberation time RT_{60} is extrapolated from the decay rate estimated by regression analysis: a least-square fit line is computed with a decay evaluation range from 5 dB to 25 dB [35]. The RT_{60} analysis may be performed on multiple bands using a filter bank. The temporal distribution of early reflections was extracted using Matlab’s *findpeaks* method, with a minimum peak distance set to 2 ms. The main objective of this approach was to have an estimation of the overall distribution of the early reflections. More advanced methods can yield more precise temporal and spatial information [36].

4. INTERACTIVE RETRIEVAL AND RENDERING

The RIR corpus is then visualised in 2D and serves as a navigation interface to browse the contained IRs while hearing the effect they have on an example signal, as explained in detail in the following.

4.1 Navigation Interface

Common to all three use cases mentioned in the introduction, the visualisation and navigation interface, depicted in figure 2, is a 2D scatterplot where each point represents one IR from the corpus. The x and y position of the points are either given by a projection to two user-selected descriptor

² <https://ircam-ismm.github.io/max-msp/mubu.html>

Descriptor Type	Descriptor Name	Explanation
Audio & Timbre	Fundamental Frequency	Mean pitch over segment [Hz]
	Loudness	Mean A-weighted loudness over segment [dB]
	Periodicity	Mean pitch strength over segment
	AC1	Mean first order autocorrelation coefficient over segment
	Spectral Centroid	Mean brightness over segment (1 st standardised moment) [Hz]
	Spectral Spread	Mean spectral spread over segment (2 nd standardised moment)
	Spectral Skewness	Mean spectral skewness over segment (3 rd standardised moment)
	Spectral Kurtosis	Mean spectral tailedness over segment (4 th standardised moment)
Room Acoustics	RT60	Broadband reverb time at -60 dB [s]
	RT60 _f	Reverb time in 7 octave bands spanning from 62.5 Hz to 4000 Hz [s]
	ER-T _i	Onset time of the <i>i</i> th early reflection [s]
	ER-A _i	Linear amplitude of the <i>i</i> th early reflection

Table 1: List of audio, timbre, and room acoustics descriptors used to characterise room impulse responses.

axes, or by the UMAP (Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection)³ graph-based dimensionality reduction algorithm [37]. UMAP has proven to be efficient in keeping points, which are neighbours in the high-dimensional descriptor space, closely together in the 2 dimensional embedding [38]. We can also mix both and use one explicit descriptor dimension for x or y, and use a one-dimensional UMAP embedding for the other axis. The colour and size of the points can be used to visualise two additional descriptor dimensions.

In the 2D navigation space, one can use the mouse pointer or a touch pad such as Sensel’s *Morph*⁴ to move the so-called *target* position in order to select the closest points’ IR for auralisation (see section 4.2 below). This corresponds to the first use case of browsing.

Alternatively, a one-dimensional embedding or choice of principal descriptor is useful for creative applications where the RIR corpus is accessed by, for instance, a MIDI keyboard with the note pitches mapped to that dimension, in order to invite playful rhythmic switching of the different IRs.

4.2 Auralisation by Convolution

To listen to the effect of the RIR selected in the navigation interface, a user-chosen test signal (an audio file played in a loop, a periodic click train, or a click triggered whenever a new IR is selected) is convolved in real-time with the selected IR.

Special care has to be taken when the target position moves closer to another point, since simply switching the IR in the convolver would result in an audible discontinuity. Instead, the input signal of the convolver is quickly faded-out with a 20 ms ramp time, and the convolution engine continues running until the end of the reverb tail (duration of the IR). At the same time, a new convolver voice is activated that receives the test signal to be convolved with the new IR. Since the user can move the target to yet another IR while the previous IR(s) are still finishing, we

³ We calculate UMAP on the normalised descriptors with 30 neighbours and minimum distance 0.1 (to spread out the resulting 2D embedding) for 200 iterations, see https://umap-learn.readthedocs.io/en/latest/how_umap_works.html for details. These values were empirically chosen to provide a usable 2D distribution of IR characteristics.

⁴ <https://sensel.com>

need a voice allocation algorithm managing up to a given number of voices of convolvers. (On the Apple Silicon M3 hardware used here, at least 32 voices can be rendered.)

This scheme realises the first use case by basically discretizing the navigation space into Voronoi-regions around each IR’s point. However, for the second use case of creative navigation and hybridisation, we allow interpolation and avoid to discretise the navigation space: While moving the mouse, the *k* closest IRs are used simultaneously and the contribution of the test signal to their input w_i is mixed according to an inverse distance-based law [39]

$$w_i = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{d_i}} \quad (1)$$

where d_i is the distance of IR *i* to the target position in the navigation space, and *k* can be chosen by the user ($k = 3$ results in a triangulation-type interpolation, $k = 1$ selects the non-interpolation use case 1). Note that this distance-based mixing still allows to hear a single IR in isolation when the target position coincides with an IR’s position.

4.3 Auralisation by Algorithmic Reverberators

For the approximation of an IR from the RIR corpus by an algorithmic reverberator of the third use case *mimic*, we use the estimated RT₆₀ reverb times and early reflection onsets to recreate the overall character of the IR. For this, we control directly the corresponding reverb parameters (reverb times in 7 frequency bands, the 20 first early reflection onset times and amplitudes) of an algorithmic FDN-based reverberator by the respective values extracted from the target RIR in the analysis phase.

4.4 Implementation

The RIRIRI browser is implemented in the MAX⁵ graphical programming environment for interactive media applications, with the MUBU⁶ [32], CATART⁷ [31], and SPAT5⁸ extension libraries. The selection, visualisation and auralisation part of the patch is shown in figure 2.

⁵ <http://cycling74.com/max>

⁶ <https://ircam-ismm.github.io/max-msp/mubu.html>

⁷ <https://ircam-ismm.github.io/max-msp/catart.html>

⁸ <https://forum.ircam.fr/projects/detail/spat>

Figure 2: Example of the navigation interface showing a corpus of RIRs according to spectral centroid and periodicity (right part), and the analysis, selection, and auralisation modules in MAX (left part).

We were able to use the CATART modules and their underlying MUBU container for time-based media and data as-is to handle RIRs and their descriptors, instead of general audio files, keeping the same structuring (one MUBU buffer for each external file, one data frame for each RIR description). CATART’s underlying architecture for importing, analysing, and selecting audio units can be reused to handle RIRs. Especially the scalable kNN unit selection [40] is completely agnostic of the audio type, since it finds nearest neighbours in a Euclidean descriptor space and outputs the ID of the closest unit(s), which is the ID of the RIR buffer (encompassing the whole RIR file, since there is no segmentation for this usage). The only difference is that the rendering is not playing back the RIR sound file as in CATART, but the IR or its parameters are used for auralisation of an example sound input: For auralisation by convolution we use `spat5.conv~` and for algorithmic approximation `spat5.tapout~` for simulation of early reflections and `spat5.elliptique~` for the tail.

The RIRIRI MAX patches will be made available in the future on the Ircam Forum.⁹

5. RESULTS

For the browsing and navigation use cases, we explored the real-world RIR collection *EchoThief*,¹⁰ sporting many

⁹ <https://forum.ircam.fr/>

¹⁰ The collection contains 116 IRs recorded in 44.1 kHz and 24 bits of 0.2 to 4.1 s duration (mean 1.28 s, std. dev. 0.7 s) and is freely down-

non-standard and outdoor locations with extreme echos, and could make the following observations:¹¹

Using the timbre descriptors, we can hear how they capture important aspects of the sound character of the IRs. Most of all, the spectral centroid restitutes very clearly the continuum from bright to dark sounding spaces.

We also notice that certain descriptors acquire a different perceptual meaning for RIRs than they would have for general sound corpora (typically constituted of instrument recordings, environmental sounds, voice, electronic sounds, etc.). For instance, the fundamental frequency descriptor latches on to the strongest resonance present in the room response and correlates to the perceived “thinness” of the acoustic space. Most strikingly, the periodicity descriptor (which is given by the strength of the autocorrelation coefficient at the fundamental frequency) corresponds perceptually to the “ringing”, “echoey”, “hollow”, or “metallic” quality of rooms, because any resonance or short flutter echo underlying these perceptions will be analysed as a strong periodic component of the sound.

We also observe that the room acoustics specific descriptors sometimes fail to cope with the unusual spaces in our test collection, leading to nonsensical values for the RT_{60} reverb time. Here, we can leverage the human curation that has produced collections like these and simply use the IR

loadable at <https://www.echothief.com>.

¹¹ See the demo video at <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLT5gV5YpSJ0z1t3bIlyfvGUTR1eDpiLGG>.

Figure 3: Correlation of Decay parameter and estimated reverb time RT_{60} (top), and of IR duration and RT_{60} (bottom) for the Little Plate plugin IR corpus.

signals’ duration as a proxy measure for reverb time. Because a sound engineer has, after all, listened to each RIR and decided on an optimal trimming point, the IR files’ durations express the contrast between short and long reverb spaces well enough to be useful for navigation.

For the third use case of examining and approximating reverb plugins, we first constituted a corpus of IRs from the plate reverb simulator plugin *Little Plate*.¹² This simple plugin offers only the two parameters *Decay* and *Low Cut* and served as validation of the room acoustics descriptors. We applied 10×10 non-uniform grid-sampling of its two parameters and recorded each setting’s output when sent a dirac impulse as input.

For this corpus we can see in figure 3 (top) that the RT_{60} descriptor does capture the reverb time very well, with a logarithmic relationship to the Decay parameter’s normalised value (which means a linear relationship to the Decay setting, which is in exponential time scale). The duration metadata descriptor (bottom) shows here a cutoff for very long reverb tails.

We then used the same procedure for the complex *FabFilter Pro-R1*¹³ reverb plugin with the 6 param-

¹² <https://www.soundtoys.com/product/little-plate>

¹³ <https://www.fabfilter.com/products/pro-r-2-reverb-plugin-in>

Figure 4: Reverb descriptor space of the FabFilter R1 plugin for use as parameter interpolator. Axes: estimated reverb time RT_{60} , centroid, colour: ER-structure reduced to one dimension by UMAP, size: decay rate parameter.

ters *Space*, *Decay Rate*, *Brightness*, *Character*, *Distance*, *Stereo Width*. When auralising with the algorithmic reverb approximation, we observe that the general character of the reverb is well captured (room size, brilliance). Finer details like the room character can not be restituted by our simpler algorithmic reverb model. However, especially when using distance-based parameter interpolation for the model, 2D navigation can function like a very detailed preset interpolator (see figure 4), preserving the overall *perceptual characteristics* of the reverb, with the two axes reverb time and centroid representing the most important parameters for a reverb, and the fine structure of IR parameter sets offering nuanced variations in the details of the algorithmic reverb. A user would then be able to fine-tune the found settings via the unified parameters of the algorithmic reverb.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we gathered insights into the usefulness of standard timbre descriptors for browsing and navigating through collections of room impulse responses. We could observe that the timbre descriptor centroid can express the brilliance, fundamental frequency the thinness, and periodicity the perceived hollowness of a space. Duration can be used as a proxy for reverb time, even for non-standard spaces.

In future work, more systematic evaluations and usability studies need to be conducted to validate the usefulness of the descriptors and the interaction paradigm. We also plan to investigate the use of mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) as a more detailed yet compact description of spectral distribution, flattened to one or two dimensions by principal component analysis (PCA), to be combined with the main timbre descriptors and the signal-domain descriptors fundamental frequency and periodicity (the latter are not well captured by the MFCC’s spectral description).

Work is under way to import and auralise multichannel spatial room impulse responses (SRIRs) in higher-order ambisonics (HOA) spherical harmonics representa-

tion. This opens the possibility to add descriptors that express also the spatial distribution or coherence of the IR of a location, and to extend each timbre descriptor by a measure of its degree of anisotropy.

After having evaluated the externally calculated room acoustics specific descriptors (reverb time, early reflections characterisation, future SRIR descriptors), we can envision to implement them as modules for the analysis framework PiPO [41], part of the MuBU package, to have them directly available in MAX. This would allow the distribution of this software to artists and sound professionals to foster experimentation with this innovative interaction paradigm in (perceptual) spaces of (acoustic) spaces.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the artistic research department of Ircam lead by Markus Noisterning as *unité projet-innovation* (UPI) RIRIRI 2024.

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